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Collaborative learning in Mathematics for Aerospace Engineering

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ABSTRACT

Learning/teaching is a complex dichotomy that with modern techniques may be unclear as it moves to a coaching and, indeed, it has been so quite often at advanced levels as Master and PhD programs. What seems to be clear after the upcoming of Bologna process is that teaching/learning is moving from a teacher centered methodology to a student centered methodology and how to implement this new approach is taking many facets such as blended learning and flipped learning. After having advanced in these two issues for a number of courses last year we have been deepening on some modalities that enhance punctually collaborative learning in Mathematics while getting

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ready for relevant moments of evaluation in the development of a Mathematics course in First Year of Aerospace Engineering at Technical University of Valencia (Valencia, Spain).

In this paper we present the activities undertaken which involve some transversal competencies such as scientific and technological communication, collaborative working and critical analysis, in addition to the specific mathematical competences.

Conference Key Areas: Mathematics and Engineering Education, Skills and Engineering Education, Continuing Engineering Education and Lifelong Learning

Keywords: Mathematics in Engineering Education, Assessment and Evaluation Strategies/Approaches, Teaching & Learning Experiences in Engineering Education, Collaborative Learning

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the objectives under the Bologna Process was to encourage students to take an active part in their own learning process [1]. This meant to turn the tables over from their usually more passive-like attitude in the classroom and several methodologies have arisen, such as problem-based learning, flipped learning, collaborative learning, online learning, etc. Combining some of these methodologies, the so called blended learning have started to emerge, so that students can learn on their own, alone or in groups, and always maintaining focus on the acquisition of specific competences during the learning process [2].

On the other hand, the competences and skills developed in the subject of Mathematics are basic in all Engineering studies, and in particular, at Aerospace Engineering where we will focus our attention, the methods being easily exportable to the rest of engineering fields. At university level magisterial classes has been the methodology traditionally used, perhaps due to the fact that usually first courses, where maths subjects are mostly allocated, have got a ratio instructors/students very high where other forms of instruction may be difficult when not impossible to be adopted.

Our groups are in the range of 50/75 students for theory and problem solving classes, numbers that drop to 25 for computing lab sessions which enable other methodologies.

The methodology used is blended since collaborative learning, flipped classroom and others, including some magister classes, are involved as detailed in Section 2. In Section 3 we comment on results and analyse the students' opinion about the collaborative learning applied in the subject. Finally, in Section 4 we discuss the results and the questionnaire with the students' opinion.

2 THE SETTING

2.1 The subject

Mathematics I is a compulsory and annual subject delivered in the first year of BEng Aerospace Engineering [3] at the Higher Technical School of Design Engineering (ETSID acronym in Spanish) of the Technical University of Valencia (Universitat Politècnica de València, UPV). It has got 12 ECTS from which 75% of them correspond to Theory/Problems (TP) sessions and the remaining 25% to Lab practice (LP).

In the Degree of Aerospace Engineering, all students should acquire the basic competence of ability to solve the mathematical problems that may arise in Engineering. This should be achieved basically through the subjects of the Department of Applied Mathematics, Mathematics I being the first of them.

In this Degree there are two different groups: one is High Academic Performance (ARA), with teaching in English, and the other not ARA, with teaching in Spanish. Both groups follow the same methodology in Mathematics classes and there is no difference in topics, assignments or exams. Language used as mean of instruction is the only difference.

Instructors of Mathematics I encourage the collaborative learning between students to develop activities related to the specific competences that must be acquired in that subject. This collaborative learning facilitates the continuous assessment of students and allows to customize their improvement needs in particular cases.

The methodology is extendible to the other mathematics subjects of this degree and in general to all those related to Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM).

2.2 On collaborative learning

Collaborative learning arises when two or more people learn or attempt to learn something together. Unlike individual learning, people engaged in collaborative learning get benefit from other's knowledge, resources and skills by asking one another for information while evaluating one's and other's ideas, resources and skills, [4-6].

Thus in collaborative learning learners engage in a common task where each individual depends on and is accountable to each other. Collaborative learning comes out when groups of students work together to search for understanding, meaning, or solutions or to create an artifact or product from their learning activities.

Hence collaborative learning redefines traditional teacher-student relationship in the classroom which some authors claim that results in controversy over whether this paradigm is more beneficial than harmful, [7-8].

In general, collaborative learning activities can include collaborative writing, group projects, joint problem solving, debates, study teams, and other activities. These different approaches bring out a wide variability in the amount of in-class or out-of-class time built around group work, [9-12]. In some approaches this collaboration arises in an unplanned form and may be closely related to cooperative learning, which is not our case as we will detail alter on.

Goals and processes of collaborative activities vary widely. Some faculty members design small group work around specific sequential steps, or tightly structured tasks. In some collaborative learning settings, the students' task is to create a clearly delineated product; in others, the task is not really produce a product, but rather to participate in a process, an exercise of responding to each other's work or engaging in analysis and meaning-making.

2.3 Our collaborative learning approach

The fundamental purpose of the application of collaborative learning is to maintain or increase the acquisition of specific competences in Mathematics, while developing the analytical and critical spirit of the students and their specific communicative competences in Mathematics.

All this is developed within a continuous evaluation process that is based on a strong increase in the number of evaluation control points.

Thus, our approach is framed as part of the process of specific competencies achievement while other transversal competencies are facilitated. For the former the traditional form of assessment is by means of individual tests but in the process collaborative and even cooperative learning might take place.

The collaborative learning is facilitated by the realization of in-class activities that are the final phase of preparation of the subject before individual traditional exams take place. Little weight and assessment are given to these pre-exam activities (15% of the theoretical/problem solving general assessment) by evaluating individual and group tests based on assignments that are made public 2 weeks in advance to the classical exam.

The assignments are designed with different level of difficulty. After they have been working on them by themselves, students can take them to the individual test so that students can consult them while performing the tests individually. We can see the students doing this test in *Fig. 1*.

Immediately after each individual test, students are required to participate in a collaboration within a small group to discuss the options that they believe valid and collect their opinion on the correct answer to each item.

We can see the students doing this work in *Fig. 2*. Collaborative groups include up to four students.

Fig. 1. Students doing the individual test

Fig. 2. Students doing the group test

In this phase student cannot use their solved test nor their solved assignments so that they must communicate and defend their choices without any support but that from their knowledge and communicative skills.

By doing this, we encourage the development of other key competencies such as oral communication skills concerning scientific and technological language, leadership, critical thinking, and ability to adapt to other environments confronting other opinions.

Students, not being able to use their individual test results, must defend their opinion by just using their oral communication skills and achieved mathematical competencies without the support of solved exercises that might simplify their posing point of view by just pointing out a result.

In this way, the potential deficiencies and strengths of their mathematical specific competencies arise while they have to use their communication skills in order to ask or defend their selected answers by discussing with peers.

Thus, the realization of the same test in group form is the facilitator of collaborative learning after the accomplishment of individual tests and is done by means of lively discussions between students just after them working introspectively each of them on the proposed exercises.

This methodology involves a greater involvement of the student in the achievement of the objectives of the course given that he/she can obtain continuous feedback of his/her level of achievement, while receiving aid in order to orient his/her efforts on those specific areas of the subject that require more practice or deeper learning.

Increasing the number of control points implies that the perception of results is more immediate, which will also result in a greater motivation of the student and a channelling of their efforts towards a homogenization in their levels of acquisition of the competences of the subject. Furthermore, the students' perception of their level of acquisition of the specific competencies increases and the collaborative discussion of their results between them facilitates the development of transversal competences such as critical analysis, problem solving and communication among others.

Finally, the early detection of students with more difficulties, makes it feasible to complement their activity in order to achieve the final objectives of the subject.

Clearly the objective is not only an increase in the number of control points of the continuous evaluation, but to facilitate the collaboration between the students so that they increase and develop both specific competencies of the subject and others of transversal type.

The specific objectives of our methodology can be summarized in:

- Facilitating collaboration among students in a group form while increasing their evaluable checkpoints. This should not imply saturation with more activities, but adapt them to collaborative learning.
- Integrating collaboration as a self-assessment and diagnostic procedure
- Encouraging the active participation of the student in the design of his / her curricular adaptation

3 RESULTS AND STUDENTS FEEDBACK

Results and rates of achievement are good as the students have very high cut marks and less than 10% of students have problems to follow it. It is necessary to have procedures that detect these situations early and guide and help them adequately.

The students' opinion on this system of work was requested. In concrete students were asked to answer some questions. The statements and the distribution of the answers are shown in *Table 1* and in *Table 2* and graphically in *Fig. 3* and in *Fig. 4*.

Table 1. Concerning the **individual tests** I think that:

	ARA	NoARA	Global
By doing them, I get aware of my level of competence and they influence my learning process	8 (16%)	14 (19%)	22 (18%)
By doing them, I do not change my perception of what I know, and they influence little on my learning process	20 (42%)	26 (35%)	46 (37%)
I would rather not do them as they do not influence on my learning process	20 (42%)	35 (46%)	55 (45%)
	48	75	123

Table 2. Concerning the group tests I think that:

	ARA	NoARA	Global
They are a good idea, and after doing them, I am more aware of my level of competence	4 (8%)	4 (5%)	8 (7%)
They are a good idea, and with them I usually learn something	23 (47%)	34 (45%)	57 (46%)
I would rather not do them as they do not influence on my learning process	8 (16%)	18 (24%)	26 (21%)
They add little value respect to the individual test, but I like doing them	4 (8%)	9 (12%)	13 (10%)
They are a loss of time	10 (20%)	10 (13%)	20 (16%)
	49	75	124

Fig. 3. Students opinion about individual tests

- (A): They help me in my learning
- (B): They influence little on my learning
- (C): They influence little on my learning and I would rather not doing them

Fig. 4. Students opinion about group tests

- (AB): They help me in my learning
- (C): They add little value to the individual test
- (DE): I would rather not doing them, they are a loss of time

Tests are done via multiple choice questions and require close attention in order to distinguish the right answer from the group of four possible answers provided for each question.

In general, we may notice that students have got a positive perspective from the collaborative part of each test and a negative one from the individual part. This may be understood if we have in mind that the first part is closely related to the previous assignment and this involves work, hard work.

When the collaborative part comes into play, interaction with mates is fun and helps them to clarify and fix ideas, and they like it. Apparently, they are not fully aware that the whole setting helps them to achieve mathematical competencies while practising with others. The final, collaborative stage, has sense in our setting once individual performance has taken place in first instance.

Perhaps they would like to skip the individual part but the input they would get from the experience would not be the same. In order to improve the perception of the students on the individual test, the instructors should make them aware of the relevance of this internal insight that enables the ulterior collaborative work based on their personal introspective work.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Due to its situation at early stages of their studies, we have considered relevant that at the same time that specific mathematics competencies are achieved by the students, they do it by facilitating the development of other transversal competencies such as scientific communication, collaboration with partners, critical thinking all of which prepare them to their continuous education and lifelong learning.

The collaborative work developed in class facilitates a deeper achievement of specific competencies. Students should be aware that this collaborative work is undertaken once they have achieved some mathematical competence and personal critical thinking that enable them to communicate and discuss with their peers. The relevance is not in the test itself or collaborative work but on the mathematical and key competencies they are developing that will get their outcome in the mathematical competencies they will show to have achieved in the ulterior individual exams.

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